

**ENGLISH LANGUAGE AS A TOOL FOR PROMOTING
TRANSPARENCY AND ACCOUNTABILITY IN
DEVELOPMENT FINANCE INSTITUTIONS (DFIs)**

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Abstract

Development Financing Institutions (DFIs) are public financial organizations established by governments with the specific focus of achieving public policy goals. DFIs must, however, function according to the principles of accountability and transparency in order to be successful. This will guarantee that financial resources are managed appropriately, stakeholders are kept informed, and trust is upheld both domestically and globally. This paper therefore aims to provide insights into the relevance of English language in ensuring and promoting accountability and transparency in DFIs. The paper points out that English acts as a unifying medium of communication because it is the most frequently spoken second language in the world and the primary language of commerce, diplomacy, and international finance. English, the paper adds, has an indisputable function in international financial reporting, auditing, policy communication, and project documentation. To guarantee access to global stakeholders, such as donors, investors, governments, and development partners, DFIs publish majority of their

contracts, press releases, yearly financial reports, and monitoring frameworks in English. This paper concludes that DFIs such as BOI DFIs can enhance their governance structures, adhere to international transparency standards, and fortify their ties with recipient communities by implementing linguistic initiatives.

Keywords: accountability, transparency, DFIs, English, reporting

Introduction

Xu et al. (2021) define development financing institutions (DFIs) as public financial organizations established by governments with the specific focus of achieving public policy goals. Typically owned by national governments, these specialized development organizations make investments in private sector projects in low- and middle-income nations (EDFI, 2020). Using a range of financial instruments, such as loans and guarantees to investors and entrepreneurs, equity participation in businesses or investment funds, and funding for public infrastructure projects, DFIs use a portion of their portfolios to invest in private sector projects in emerging economies in order to fulfill their mandate. In addition to making money, DFIs make investments to assist a nation's sustainable transition route by encouraging the development of jobs and sustainable economic growth (EDFI, 2020).

Indian and Malaysian governments have defined DFIs as public financial institutions established by national governments in support of overall social and economic development, while the Association of European Development Finance Institutions (EDFI) defines DFIs as public financial institutions established by high-income country governments in support of private sector development in developing countries (Fernandez-Arias et al., 2020; Ferraz, 2017). Despite originating in the 20th century, DFIs have seen a sharp increase in significance and portfolio diversification during the last 15 to 20 years (Savoy, Carter, & Lemma, 2016). Due in large part to the reinvestment of earnings, DFIs increased their annual non-sovereign private development investments from USD 12 billion in 2000 to USD 87 billion in 2017, a six-fold increase in just 17 years (Publish What You Fund, 2020). This growth is in line with the 2015 Addis Ababa Conference on Finance for Development's proposal for a more explicit role for DFIs and a surge in private sector involvement in emerging countries (United Nations, 2015).

Development Finance Institutions (DFIs) like the World Bank, the African Development Bank (AfDB), and the Bank of Industry (BOI) in Nigeria are vital to the modern global economy because they finance infrastructure projects, encourage inclusive growth, and drive sustainable development. In order to promote economic growth, lessen poverty, and tackle global issues like inequality and climate change, these institutions organize and distribute funds to the public and private sectors. DFIs must, however, function according to the principles of accountability and

transparency in order to be successful. This will guarantee that financial resources are managed appropriately, stakeholders are kept informed, and trust is upheld both domestically and globally (Kerzner, 2017; Osei-Kyei & Chan, 2015).

According to Oxfam (2018), public accountability, informed decision-making, and effective governance are all predicated on openness and information availability. Inclusionary, high-impact development that significantly enhances the lives of marginalized and vulnerable individuals living in poverty as well as the larger society in which they reside is made possible by open and transparent processes. There is a genuine and pressing need for transparency and disclosure of project-related information for marginalized and vulnerable groups. This is demonstrated by the instances in which civil society organizations have revealed environmental damage and violations of human rights resulting from projects funded by development finance institutions (DFIs) and supported by financial intermediaries, in which communities and stakeholders were not provided with access to pertinent project information, its financiers, or the standards and protections that ought to have been in place (Oxfam, 2015).

The English language is among the most effective yet underutilized tools for improving accountability and transparency in DFIs. In cross-border commercial transactions, English acts as a unifying medium of communication because it is the most frequently spoken second language in the world and the primary language of commerce, diplomacy, and international finance. It has an indisputable function in international financial reporting, auditing, policy communication, and project documentation. To guarantee access to global stakeholders, such as donors, investors, governments, and development partners, DFIs, for example, publish majority of their contracts, press releases, yearly financial reports, and monitoring frameworks in English. Thus, financial accounting is sometimes referred to as "the language of business" (Fülbier & Sellhorn, 2023). That is, financial accounting is a communication tool where information senders aim to be understood by recipients by being cooperative (Grice 1975), that is, "accurate (maxim of truth) and complete (maxim of quantity), while communicating in ways that are relevant to the listener (maxim of relation) and as brief and clear as possible (maxim of manner)" (Bloomfield, 2008). When done correctly, corporate reporting improves information quality, or transparency, which includes clarity, accuracy, and disclosure.

Despite the importance of communication in financial governance, there is still little scholarly discussion on the connection between language, especially English, and the advancement of accountability and transparency in DFIs. The majority of DFI research has focused on topics including project performance, governance frameworks, and funding methods (Seboka & Gidebo, 2025). Despite their

importance, the linguistic aspect of accountability and transparency has received relatively little study.

For example, Aburous and Kamla (2022) investigated linguistic conflicts in the field of professional accounting, concentrating on English linguistic capital, accountants' distinctiveness, hierarchy, and prestige. The methods by which English language capital was validated as essential to the status, differentiation, and prestige of professional accountants in Jordan were investigated in the Aburous and Kamla's (2022) study. Their study, which drew on 27 interviews, showed how social hierarchies and Jordanian accountants' agency in integrating the English language into daily routines and practices were dynamic and mutually dependent.

Senior accountants used English language techniques and methods related to the global accounting frameworks. Aburous and Kamla (2022) held that because of their affluent, socially and economically privileged upbringing, these individuals usually already spoke English well. In contrast, even though they were more fluent in Arabic, less influential accountants who were not from the elite tend to embrace and absorb the necessity of English in their line of work. Their coping strategies mainly served to solidify their marginalization, even though they occasionally succeeded in creating opportunities for hybrid language practices by altering the usage of Arabic and English to fit their practical everyday demands. According to the data presented by Aburous and Kamla (2022), all of the Jordanian accountants in their study, irrespective of their social status, felt the emotional effects of the conflicts between the meanings that English and Arabic had because of colonial history and the global need for English in their line of work.

In another study, Guan et al. (2025) looked at how language affects information loss and the adoption of IFRS. The study looked at whether and how a nation's decision to implement International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) is impacted by linguistic obstacles. The results show that the likelihood and speed of a country adopting IFRS diminish with the linguistic distance, i.e. the distance between a country's official language and English. This supports the idea that financial reporting preparers and users incur substantial information costs due to language barriers, making the adoption of IFRS more expensive in nations with high language barriers. Subsequent investigation revealed that when these nations eventually implement IFRS, these information costs become apparent. Overall, the study indicates that language limitations raise the costs of adopting, comprehending, and using IFRS, which obstructs the goal of worldwide accounting harmonization.

Therefore, this article is important for a number of reasons in light of this perceived gap. Through its integration with the discourse of development finance and governance, it broadens the scope of language and communication studies. The

language aspects of accountability are also highlighted, which is an area of the literature that has received little attention. The results offer valuable information to DFIs like the World Bank, AfDB, and BOI about how language usage and choice affect stakeholder communication impact. English that is easy to understand and use can increase credibility and trust, while too much complexity might undermine it. Development finance policymakers can gain insight into how properly utilized English encourages accountability, but it may also be necessary to add local languages to guarantee inclusivity. DFIs can enhance their governance structures, adhere to international transparency standards, and fortify their ties with recipient communities by implementing linguistic initiatives.

Transparency and Accountability in DFIs

In modern governance, the idea of accountability and openness in the public sector has grown in importance. Ensuring effective financial management and prudent decision-making is crucial because governments are in charge of overseeing public finances and providing residents with necessities (Amalia, 2023). In an effort to promote trust, lessen corruption, and enhance general governance, the public and stakeholders have been calling for increased accountability and transparency in the public sector in recent years. Accountability and transparency are seen as essential to DFIs' legitimacy and long-term viability. Kerzner (2017) defines accountability as the duty of DFIs to notify stakeholders of and defend their decisions, whereas transparency is the clarity, openness, and accessibility of information supplied by institutions. After reviewing research on public-private partnerships, Osei-Kyei and Chan (2015) discovered that poor accountability systems and a lack of transparency were two of the most frequently mentioned reasons why projects failed.

Transparency is therefore crucial to establishing and sustaining public discourse as well as raising public knowledge of the development role and objective of DFIs (Kenny, 2020). It is also essential for improving accountability, development efficacy, and good governance. Being transparent encourages interaction with stakeholders, which enhances project and policy design and execution and fortifies development results. DFIs create investments and use public fund to help people in developing nations. The intended beneficiaries as well as the taxpayers who supply the funding have a right to know how this money is being used. This is particularly true when it comes to the allocation of noncompetitive subsidies, which presents further governance issues. All stakeholders will feel more confident that development funding is a wise use of tax if there is increased transparency.

Transparency increases the pipeline of high-quality projects by letting prospective clients know what to anticipate from working with a DFI. Additionally, it boosts any demonstrative effect of subsidy-related programs. By proving the feasibility of a new productive activity in an economy, a customized subsidy given to a single

company offering a new service or product in a market serves to promote knowledge spillover (Kenny, 2020). All businesses may better grasp the expenses and market for the new product or service by knowing the terms and specifics of the initiatives. Once more, transparency will lessen the possibility of DFIs competing for projects based on the size of the subsidies they provide. The development impact of DFI investments is considerably diminished by subsidy competition.

Transparency helps safeguard those who may suffer harm as a result of a project funded by the DFI. According to Oxfam (2018), there is an immediate and genuine demand for transparency and disclosure of project-related information for marginalized and vulnerable people. The concern is on-lending through financial intermediaries, which seems to disregard the rules and principles established by DFIs to guarantee more accountability following years of education, even if numerous problematic sub-financed projects have surfaced.

The Role of Language in Governance and Development

Language is a potent instrument for development, social inclusion, and governance in addition to being a means of communication. The clarity of language employed in financial institutions and public administration reports, rules, and regulations has a direct impact on public trust and compliance. According to Altbach (1991), English frequently serves as a lingua franca in situations involving interactions between local and international stakeholders, facilitating mutual understanding across linguistic barriers. Scholars like Hutchinson and Torres (1994), have noted that language can serve as an "agent of change," influencing decision-making and forming beliefs, particularly when it comes to official documents and textbooks. Similar to this, the communication language used in development finance affects how approachable, open, and reliable institutional procedures seem. Poor accountability systems, corruption, and misunderstandings are all made possible by inadequate communication (Issitt, 2004).

According to Ihejirika (2020), given the nature of language and governance, one may argue without any fear of contradiction that language plays a key role in government. In the first place, governance is not an abstract thing, it is personified in actors and actresses, who are essentially men and women that make decisions and implement them within their regions of jurisdiction. For one to participate effectively as an actor or actress in the process of governance, it is apparent that one should develop intellectually, educationally, socially and of course technologically. None of these elements of human growth can be fully fulfilled in the absence of language. For instance, in the case of intellectual development, whereas it is a psychological process, it is measured in terms of language use. One who develops physically but cannot utilize language properly could be said to be

retarded mentally, which could give birth to poor intellectual growth. Thus, intellectual development, which is an ingredient in governance, cannot be devoid of language since “no stage of intellectual development can be successfully attained without language development and utilization” (Jiboku, 2002).

Another component in human growth where language plays an essential role is education. Education, whether formal or informal, is a veritable agent for development and language is the human means of expressing the subject (Ogbodo, 2003). This concept is highly enhanced by Iheakaram (2001) as he argues language is like Air and Time (LAT) in the life of humans. It is invisible, more or less silent and yet necessary. It has long reaching implications on our life. These are the reasons why there is no substitute for language in the schooling process. It is therefore the most crucial aspect in education at all levels and in all forms since without it there can be no education.

The place of language in governance can also be addressed from the standpoint of communication. Communication as a process of giving and receiving information is a highly crucial part in governance. The rationale is that there is the need for the government to reach the governed and the governed in turn should respect the government by engaging actively in the process of governance. This relationship between the government and governed can only be fully achieved where there is free flow of information through the mass media, which may be local, print or electronic. It is in acknowledgment of the vital role mass communication plays in governance that Otagburuagu (2004) believes that mass communication is crucial in democratic government as it provides a quick mechanism for the transmission of information and the pulling together of public opinion. Besides, government laws, policies and judgments are designed to be documented, kept for future reference and for the generation yet unborn. All these features of communication as stated, which strengthen governance, are basically unattainable in the absence of language.

In another contribution, Chinaguh (2025) stated that language is a cornerstone of national development, acting as a critical tool for society advancement and cultural transmission. It enhances knowledge transfer, fosters literacy, and enables citizens to participate effectively in political and economic processes. Education, a cornerstone of national development, is profoundly connected with language, which works as the major medium for instruction and knowledge transmission (Owu-Ewie & Eshun, 2015). Politically, language helps governance by ensuring that policies and government programmes are successfully conveyed and understood by citizens. Language fosters economic development by enabling effective communication, promoting trade, and fostering innovation. Additionally, it empowers individuals to participate in the labor and entrepreneurial pursuits.

In essence, language is vital to government, as it serves as the medium for communication, policy implementation, and decision-making. It is a crucial instrument for documenting national growth, conserving historical achievements, cultural values, and policy frameworks for future generations. It enables nations to communicate visions, document successes, and assure continuity in government (Chinaguh, 2025). Clear and accessible communication in governance ensures that citizens comprehend government policies, laws, and regulations, hence boosting compliance and minimizing bureaucratic inefficiencies (Ihejirika, 2020).

English, Transparency and Institutional Accountability

English has become the primary language used in international finance. The majority of regional DFIs, the World Bank, and the International Monetary Fund (IMF) all use it as their working language. According to Altbach (1991), English is widely used in academic and technical publishing and distribution, which strengthens its standing in institutional and professional discourse. Oates (2014) goes on to say that in order to remain consistent and credible in front of audiences around the world, organizations must use standardized English reporting. The majority of the AfDB's main publications in Africa are published in English and French, reflecting the organization's regional and international commitments. However, due to its widespread recognition as the language of business and diplomacy, English frequently takes primacy in international negotiations, contracts, and financial reporting. Because of this dominance, being able to communicate in English becomes essential for gaining access to, understanding, and influencing DFI policy.

When Riveros et al. (2022) looked at contract management in public projects, they found that confusing reporting and poorly explained terms were major factors in early contract termination. Similar findings were made by Seboka and Gidebo (2025), who looked at contract administration in Ethiopia and discovered that ambiguous or inaccessible reporting frequently resulted in accountability gaps. These studies highlight how crucial effective communication is to responsibility, with language playing a major role.

The uniformity of reports, audits, and policy declarations is the connection between English and openness. The World Bank and AfDB, for instance, write their annual reports in English to ensure compatibility with international accounting standards and to enable for worldwide examination. According to Pingel (2010), using a standardized language in institutional reporting fosters credibility and comparability.

Even in non-English speaking nations, a large number of businesses publish yearly reports in English (Jeanjean, Lesage, & Stolowy, 2010). Businesses update investors and analysts on previous events and future plans through their annual

report. Research findings and surveys have confirmed that the annual report is an essential source of information for analysts worldwide. Investment decisions are based on the annual report. Therefore, it involves more than just reading and evaluating yearly reports. To gain answers to questions that come up after reviewing public documents, it also entails speaking with the company's management, other staff members, rival businesses, and others (Stowe, Robinson, Pinto, & McLeavey, 2007). One of the most important components of financial reports' worldwide comparability is their language. In other words, understanding the language used in the annual report is a necessary but not sufficient requirement for an analyst to do his duties effectively. It is critical to comprehend the elements that influence the decision to use English for financial reporting.

DFIs expand their investor base and visibility by employing English in their external reports. This is known as the awareness hypothesis or investor base hypothesis (Merton, 1987). The advantage of employing English as a reporting language, according to this idea, is that it exposes DFIs to more possible investors, increasing their investor base and lowering their value discount. The favorable correlation between using English and expanding the pool of possible investors is due to a number of variables. English is a lingua franca: 93% of financial analysts who are members of the CFA Institute are based in English-speaking nations, stock exchanges in English-speaking nations account for 65% of global stock market capitalization, and English is the second most spoken language in the world (after Mandarin). Thus, ownership concentration, the necessity for outside funding, and national characteristics are linked to the need to increase the investor base (Jeanjean et al. 2010).

Shannon and Weaver's (1949) communication model can be relevant here. Although it was created to simulate the telecommunication conditions that dictate a signal's transmission, it also encapsulates communication as an endeavor on both sides of the process to send and receive a message on a specific medium, a process that is endangered by noise sources in particular and entropy in general. According to Al-Fedaghi (2012), the Shannon and Weaver model of communication provides an example of how communication is conducted and how various communication channels affect the way a message is conveyed, understood, and received. In the context of DFIs, communication occurs through reports, financial statements, contracts, and press releases with English serving as the primary channel.

Reducing "noise," which can include imprecise language, technical jargon, or inconsistent terminology, is necessary for effective communication (Oates, 2014). Transparency is promoted, for instance, when the BoI's or the African Development Bank's (AfDB) annual reports are released in plain English, making it easier for governments, investors, and donors to understand financial data. On the other hand, the "noise" increases when excessively technical or complex English is used, which

can result in intentional obfuscation or misunderstandings. Communication Theory thus establishes a direct connection between language and transparency outcomes by emphasizing the crucial role that English plays in guaranteeing correctness, clarity, and accessibility in DFI communication.

Furthermore, information asymmetry, the situation in which agents have more information than principals, is a major problem in agency partnerships. If accountability systems are inadequate, this mismatch may result in corruption, poor management, or opportunism. In order to lessen this disparity, English usage in DFIs is essential. By making information publicly available and globally accessible, the BoI, for instance, lessens the knowledge gap between managers and stakeholders when it publishes its financial audits and project monitoring reports in English. Since agents (DFIs) must defend their acts to principals (stakeholders), transparent communication in English thus turns into an accountability tool. Agency theory (Jensen & Meckling, 1976) does, however, clearly highlight certain drawbacks. Asymmetry may be maintained if reports are prepared in extremely technical English, which could disfavor principals who lack the necessary financial or language proficiency. This realization is essential to comprehending why accessible disclosure is just as important as disclosure in terms of transparency.

However, the role of English is not without challenges. Official papers frequently utilize extremely technical English, which makes it harder for the general people to understand. Even though the organization may assert that it has released information, openness is compromised when financial statements, contracts, and monitoring reports are rife with technical terms. English may therefore decrease accessibility at the local level even as it encourages responsibility on a global scale. According to Wali et al. (2024), local policymakers frequently lacked access to regression-based models in groundwater research due to the reports' exclusive use of technical English. According to these results, localized communication techniques are crucial for inclusivity even though English improves global accountability.

A number of approaches are put up by academics to resolve the conflict between local inclusivity and English dominance. Technical English should be used for global stakeholders, whereas plain English (or translated versions) should be used for grassroots communities (Hutchinson & Torres, 1994). Plain language policies are another recent innovation that encourages DFIs to write reports in easily readable English free of superfluous jargon. For example, organizations all around the world have been motivated to make official documents easier to understand by the UK's Plain English Campaign. In addition, bilingual or multilingual reporting (English + local languages) has been suggested as a means of striking a balance between community inclusivity and international standards in the African context (Oates, 2014).

Conclusion

Development finance institutions (DFIs) are specialized development banks established to aid in the development of the private sector in underdeveloped nations. The majority of them are often controlled by national governments, and they get government guarantees or cash from international or national development funds. By doing this, they may raise a lot of money on global financial markets and offer financing on extremely favorable conditions because it guarantees their creditworthiness. DFIs must, however, function according to the principles of accountability and transparency in order to be successful. This will guarantee that financial resources are managed appropriately, stakeholders are kept informed, and trust is upheld both domestically and globally (Osei-Kyei & Chan, 2015). This not unconnected to the fact that English acts as a unifying medium of communication because it is the most frequently spoken second language in the world and the primary language of commerce, diplomacy, and international finance.

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